

Bharati Mukherjee's novel *The Tiger's Daughter*: Study of Social Trends and Recognition

Paper Id : 18554 Submission Date : 10/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 19/02/2024 Publication Date : 25/02/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10785519

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Abstract

The Tiger's Daughter embodies the loneliness and nostalgia for a class and culture. The novel is quite natural because it is her expression of the expatriate consciousness. The protagonist of this novel is Tara who returns Indian for a visit. The paper throws light on her novel, which narrates the return of an immigrant, Tara Banerjee, to India in the hope of recovering her roots and the sensibility of her cultural identity as an Indian. But the wistful, passionate sensitivity of immigrant for her mother country is dashed to pieces when it comes into direct blows with reality. She visits India to reconnect with her rich culture and gain a deeper understanding of her Bengali Indian culture. She is trying to focus on changed situation after seven years and also depicts the variation of two cultures.

Keywords Cross-Culture, Cultural Identity, Female Identity, Immigrants, Tradition.

Introduction

Bharati Mukherjee is an activist of civil rights, educator, an author of highly praised novels, short stories and non-fiction works. She draws her own life experiences to navigate and transcend cultural boundaries. In her role as a diasporic writer, she articulates the complexities of cultural identity, the immigrant experience, and the feelings of displacement and dislocation. Mukherjee's novels delineate the female identity, culture, tradition, myth and the sensibility for the cross-culture crisis in the period of globalization.

Objective of study

This novel is a fictionalized story drawing from Mukherjee's own first years of marriage and her return home for a visit to a world unlike the one that lives in her memory. It addresses her personal difficulties of being caught between two worlds, homes as well as cultures. It is an examination of who is she and where she belongs.

Review of Literature

Bharati Mukherjee is an activist of civil rights, educator, an author of highly praised novels, short stories and non-fiction works. She utilizes her own personal experiences in crossing the cultural boundaries. As a diasporic writer she defines the cultural identity, experience of immigrants and the sense of displacement and dislocation. Mukherjee's novels delineate the female identity, culture, tradition, myth and the sensibility for the cross-culture crisis in the period of globalization. The distorts psyche of those immigrants who had been surviving in the conflict of traditional Indian values which innate in their personality. The tremendous difference between two types of life, leads a person to a feeling of depression and frustration.

"While in Canada, Bharati Mukherjee published two novels, *The Tiger's Daughter* in 1971 and *Wife* in 1975. She also co-authored a book of memoirs with her husband, entitled *Day and Night in Calcutta* (1977), on their year-long stay in India in 1973-74, after a fire in their Montreal home. Other writings in Canada included articles on civil rights such as "An Invisible Woman" and a few short stories which were later published in the collection *Darkness* (1985). Another collaborative effort with her husband was published in the U.S.A. - *The Sorrow and the Terror* (1987), on the 1985 crash of the Air India plane *Kanishka*, travelling from Toronto to Bombay. Mukherjee's collection of short stories *The Middleman and Other Stories* (1988) has won critical recognition and awards. Subsequently there has been on more novel *Jasmine*"[1]

Main Text

Bharati Mukherjee, an Indian-American immigrant writer, liberates her women protagonists for a "New World Order". Mukherjee depicts women characters inspired from her experiences in India as well as abroad. Her main characters, shaped by sensitivity, struggle with an unsettled personal and cultural identity. These protagonists face victimization, encountering racism, sexism, and various forms of social oppression. Bharati Mukherjee is concerned with characters that strain and struggle for the articulation of their repressed and stunted voice. As a writer she likes to put much stress on the fact that her characters, whether they are uniquely Indian or superficially Western, are basically human. Her women characters vent their feminine sensibility in their frantic desire for an authentic communication with their own selves as well as with the society.

"Bharati Mukherjee's novels, we get a graphical pattern of a female immigrant's self-satisfaction in proportion to the approach she adopts to deal with the dilemma of being out-rooted but still connected. Significantly, it is the revised or modified forms of these concepts that define their typical existence." [2]

These types of themes can be easily identified in works of immigrant writers of Indian English literature. Bharati Mukherjee's novels deal with the problem of female suppression but on the other side she gives a new identity to the women of modern times. Bharati Mukherjee portrays the character of Tara Banerjee as the new woman who adopts the new lifestyle in an alien country. She makes her identity in new groups that are shaped by the culture and tradition of her adopted country but also influenced by her motherland. Her early work led to her being seen as a writer firmly enclosed in the bosom of Indian writing in English. But this was an embrace that Mukherjee herself sought to avoid. With the publication of *Darkness*, her third book of fiction, she convincingly declared her desire to be seen as a North American writer.

"Bharati Mukherjee, now settled abroad, is a significant woman novelist. Born in 1940, she went to the U.S.A in 1961. Even though it is more than three decades since she left India for the American continent, familial ties continue to bind her to the country of her birth. But she is clear about where her loyalties lie today and is at pains to emphasize that she is an American writer. She has been greatly attached to Calcutta. Since she was born and brought up there, she says, "the city will remain a habit with me, but as a writer, I have developed entirely in the United States." Mukherjee's writing career began in 1971, with *The Tiger's Daughter*." [3]

Bharati Mukherjee deals with the themes related to Indian women particularly the problem of identity crisis, cross-cultural issue and search for identity. She also depicts the clashes between two cultures and caste. Her protagonist tries to tackle the problem of loss of culture and established a new identity in the U.S. This cultural transplant leads to a crisis of identity and becomes an expression of our governing systems of ethnicity, race and religion, interacting with the social, economic and political world around us.

"India is safely in the camp of democracy, whether science and technology are compatible with tradition values in Indian life and whether India can be assured of increasing prosperity are chiefly because of inadequate recognition of India's attempt, throughout the age, at a reconciliation of the opposing forces of enjoyment and renunciation. There are also misconceptions regarding the pillars of the Indian social structure namely the joint family, the caste and self-sufficient village community." [4]

In this way, cultural identity represents the extent we feel connected to the part of a given cultural group. While identity formation is a fluid construct which is subject to evolution and influence, one could argue that people born to the dominant in-group experience a relatively smooth and unvaried transition into their sense of self. Conversely, first- or second-generation immigrants who have stake in two different worlds may find themselves stuck by conflicting values, practices and identities. Indeed, globalization has opened up the door for culture to flow between time and space.

Bharati Mukherjee has also explored the positive and negative aspects of multiculturalism. She places her protagonists in a various situation where they find different cultures and traditions. She portrays the different types of situations in her novels like the journey for quest of identity, struggles between the two cultures, alienation, rootlessness, loneliness, isolation and dislocation. She draws her characters who remain connected to their homeland. In *The Tiger's Daughter*, *Desirable Daughters* and *The Tree Bride*, *The Holder of the World*, *leave it to Me*, these are the stories in which her character always remain their roots and native lands. In such a multicultural background, they go through identity crisis which leads them to undertake a quest of their own identity.

“The religious individual is not closed off against the world and the society in which he lives. In a dual manner, he is open in relation to these. Logically, prior to any ‘religious experience’ he has received from society a whole host of symbols, concepts and spontaneous emotive associations connected with these. They flow into his experience and flavor it and provide a social or ‘cultural’ dimension to it. Nobody could even identify in his own consciousness a religious experience, had he not learnt from society the words and their meaning, of ‘experience’ and ‘religious’. This example also shows that, naturally, ‘culture’ encompasses a much wider range of words, concepts and symbols than what we would call ‘religious.’”[5]

Cultural alienation is a huge problem today. This can be termed as culture shock when a person moves away from their own culture and old values come into clash with the new ones which they find. Bharati Mukherjee describes the American immigration experience as one of a “two-way process” in which both the writer and the immigrants grow by the interchange and experience.

“Eliot believes that there is a very close relationship between culture and religion. It is religion of a people which makes them culturally different from the people of other faiths. Two religions may have something in common but their differences might bring about a clash among their followers. It is really very difficult to reconcile between two antagonistic religions. Eliot begins his enquiry into the relationship between culture and religion with a very important assertion: - “No culture has appeared or developed except together with religion ...culture will appear to be the product of religion, or the religion the product of the culture.”[6]

Mukherjee brings American and Indian culture together, especially the Bengali culture. In her novels she mainly focuses on Bengali culture and traditions. Which are deeply rooted in her characters. Marriage is a social connotation culture that ties a man and woman into a relationship intending mutual understanding and support between them. It reflects the culture of a particular community, group, religion etc. In a novel *The Tiger's Daughter* Mukherjee handles marriage as the second important theme. “It is, thus apparent that culture owes much of its existence to religion. An individual, class or group or a society's way of living is molded and shaped by its religion which in turn becomes that religion of that particular society. In other words, we can say that culture and religion are complementary to each other. Viewing the deep affinity between them, Eliot dilates: -

“And both ‘religion’ and ‘culture’ besides meaning different things from each other, should mean for the individual and for the group something towards which they strive, not merely something which they possess. Yet these are an aspect in which we can see a religion as the whole way of life of a people, from birth to the grave, from morning to night and even in sleep, and that way of life is also its culture.”[7]

In the novel *The Tiger's Daughter* Tara plans a trip to India in search of the Indian memories. Which also reflects the conflict between illusion and reality. But the novelist has adopted the technique of documentation to bring out the contrast between two cultures and two worlds. An immigrant away from home idealizes their home country and fond memories of it. Tara is packed off by her father at early age of fifteen for America because he is prompted by suspicion and pain about his country. But in foreign land sometime she feels homesick and even small things cause her pain. Bharati Mukherjee, an Indian-born writer. She distinguishes herself from many European writers for several reasons, making her a notable figure among American immigrant writers. There are many such features in Bharati Mukherjee's literature, which differentiate her writings from other European writers. Bharati Mukherjee's female protagonists are immigrants and suffered from cultural shock but they are potential women and anxious to establish their identity by undertaking their heroic journeys. This is the reason Bharati Mukherjee has received considerable critical attention from almost all the quarters of the globe in a relatively short period of just twenty-five years. Even though she has been acknowledged as a “voice of expatriate-immigrants” sensibility, a close observation of her novels reveals that she has written all the novels with predominantly feminist views.

Since Bharati Mukherjee's women characters are the victims of immigration, all the critics focus her novels as problems and consequences due to immigration but the problems are not because they the characters in Mukherjee's works are immigrants, yet they stand out because the female protagonists actively advocate for their rights both as women and individuals. Mukherjee endeavors to establish a redefined relationship between men and women, emphasizing equality as a cornerstone.. In Bharati Mukherjee's first novel *The Tiger's Daughter*, the protagonist Tara Banerjee returns to India after seven years stay in America. The story is drawn on Mukherjee's own experience and those of her sisters who had gone to study in America.

When Tara lands to India, her first stepping at Bombay fills her disappointment. The unfamiliar territory appears to have transformed into a place that feels more like home to her. She repents to have come to India without her husband and she is unable to keep him off her mind. "Perhaps I was stupid to come without him, she thought, even with him rewriting his novel during the vacation. Perhaps I was too impulsive, confusing my fear of New York with homesickness. Or perhaps I was going mad." [8] She is not comfortable with her relatives. Here, Tara's Bombay relatives cannot accept a woman who not accompanied by her husband, David. According to Indian tradition, a man should lead the woman, he plays a protective role. Travelling alone, living alone and moving alone are part of unfamiliarity in many parts of India.

In Indian tradition, one should marry in his own caste, if anyone marries from another caste, they will be treated as an outcast or a sinner. Tara, the main character, goes against these norms by marrying a foreign man who is a Jewish. "In India she felt she was not married to a person but to a foreigner and this foreignness was a burden. It was hard for her to talk about marriage responsibilities in Camac Street, her friends were curious only about the adjustments she has made." [9] She is totally forgetting her caste and religion through her marriages. The primary factor intensifying her sense of discomfort and unease is her marriage, which weighs heavily on her heart like a burden.

When Tara Banerjee landed in Bombay, after seven years, there she realized that she forgot her Bengali culture and this is the reason to know much more about her culture and for rerooting herself she visits to India. "Tara's mother, Arati, was a saintly woman. At least, she was given to religious dreams. Her religious dreams were not holy enough to turn her hair white overnight. But they were adequately religious." [10] Tara's mother is a very kind and virtuous woman. All the day she is doing *Pooja Path*. She spends most of her time in god's prayer. "As a saintly woman, Tara's mother spent a great deal of time in the prayer room." [11]

Tara's mother is a spiritual kind of lady; she follows all her cultural rules. She takes three times bath in a day. "The saintly mother also spent an unreasonable amount of time in the bathroom next to dressing room. Taking three baths a day was a principle with her." [12] Taking three-time baths in a day is her principle, because she does not like to touch the god from dirty hands. When Tara's mother sits in her prayer, she does not want any kind of disturbance during her worship. When Tara thought to leave *Pooja* room then her mother said "Don't leave," her mother said, swiveling slightly on her tiny carpet but not breaking the rhythm of her Sanskrit prayers." [13] She doesn't want to pay attention to any kind of sound during her prayers.

Mukherjee makes a criticism of the conservative attitude of the Indians who are crazy of foreign things and clothes but they do not accept the marriage with foreign people. In the presence of her mother, Tara feels alienated within herself. Tara becomes mentally turbulent and makes her return to the USA. In this way Tara's journey to India proves as a quest for self and quest for immigrant psyche which prove frustrating slowly leading to her illusion, alienation, depression and finally her tragic end.

Conclusion

In the novel *The Tiger's Daughter*, Mukherjee explores the journeys of both an Indian expatriate and an American migrant. She also highlighting the issues of women experience different challenges, struggle for adaptation and social norms which is faced by female character. The novel introduces a convincing perspective in diasporic literature. The main theme of this novel is an Indian woman who relocates to the United States and reshaping her connections to her native land. Tara has been displaced from her native land due to an unexpected connection with a man from a different cultural background. She finds herself suspended between the familiarity of her original homeland and the challenges of her newly adopted one. It's akin to selecting the superior of two perspectives. Tara holds this dilemma, experiences a period of uncertainty, and ends up in an ambiguous territory. Yet, having gained insights from both environments, she employs her judgement wisely. Ultimately, she opting for her recently adopted native land. Marriage and international travel bring about physical and mental transformations in the personal lives of women. Despite their evident flexibility, their experience plays a pivotal role in shaping their journey. Having originated and grown up in India. They are raising a profound desire to free themselves from cultural limitations and embrace a Western lifestyle, even if it appears somewhat fantastical. Their vocal support for feminism and liberation, putting these ideals into action. Which proves to be a challenge for Mukherjee's female characters, emerging as the most demanding aspect of their existence.

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